

Research Article

**The Non-Accessibility of E-books by Students of Technical Education Programmes:
its Benefits, and Implication to Learning**

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Abstract

In today's world of digital technology, the wider and faster ways of publishing e-books by anybody makes more information to be easily accessible in both online and downloaded format. It is no longer news that various websites are now hosting many Electronic-Book materials in larger volume than to what the biggest library in the world could host. This is a booming business for revenue generation in many countries of the world. This paper examines the benefits of EBooks publishing, reduction of paper in circulation, and its implication to learning through plagiarism and fatigue. Three questions and hypotheses were designed, formulated, and tested. This study employed a descriptive research method that involves 100 respondents using a survey instruments administered to the selected subjects. The completed questionnaires were analyzed using inferential statistics of chi-square in order to accept or reject the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Findings revealed that lecturers and students do not have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performance. One of the recommendations made is that, all institution bodies concerned should device a means of encouraging lecturers to publish eBooks and check students plagiarism as this is one of the issues of electronic books.

**Keywords: Technology, Technical Education, Paper circulation,
Electronic books**

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Introduction

The objective of this paper is to examine the benefits of EBooks publishing, reduction of paper in circulation, and its implication to learning through plagiarism and fatigue. It focuses on whether or not students access electronic-books in the college library to improve their academic performances and if lecturers make use of the college website for uploading their teaching and learning contents in this digital era. Gone were those days when you need to find your way to the town library for books that are not on your home library, probably for assignment, projects, or for reading sake. One cannot even be sure of its availability because many people might even be looking for the same material or book at the same time. Moreover, if one is able to go for such a book and then checked it out, the policy is that there is always an ultimatum to return the book back. At times when such books are not available, one needs to purchase them even at an exorbitant price. In today's world, the story line has changed from paper book to electronic book, as a result of technology. Technology in this perspective is the application of scientific knowledge leading to new discoveries, innovations, and new changes that are inspiring. It has to do with making things work better, bringing comfort and ease to human lives and the society we live in. One of the technological tools this paper is focusing on is electronic books (popularly refers to as eBook) in this digital era.

Literature Review

EBooks according to Nelson (2008) are books that can be read digitally with the aid of a screen, either on mobile phones, computer set, or eBook readers. Many traditional printed books are found in electronic formats without much stress or time wasting. In today's world, eBooks are in high demands and it is making big sales over some other technologies like our mobile phones. According to Nelson (2008), government of China acquired 165 million eBook readers for her students. The Computer world new reported in February 2012 shows that, the New York Public Library checked out 2,907 e-books and materials on December. 26, 2011 as against 1,523 that was checked out on December 26, 2010. This is just in a single day. In addition, looking at the sales of e-books from a global perspectives, in 2006, Japan made sales of \$182 million US dollars; Korea made sales of \$144 million US dollars while United States of America (U.S.A) made about \$ 20 million (Nelson, 2008). Nevertheless, to the surprise, in the third quarter of 2010, U.S.A. made sales of \$1.62 billion dollars (Reid, 2011). However, between 2011 and 2015, event changed as indicated below.

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The biggest publishing markets in 2013 and 2014 shows that two major markets compete to be ranked, as the world's biggest. This is the United State of America and European Union. The total revenue for US publishers in 2013 was €24.2 billion (26.7 billion USD), and the total revenue for publishers in the European Union (EU) was €22.3 billion (Annual Report October 2014 – October 2015 Global Publishing and Reading Statistics).

Table 1: The biggest publishing markets in 2013 for which figures are available 2014

<i>Country</i>	<i>Revenue M€</i>	<i>Revenue MLC</i>	<i>Market Value M€</i>	<i>Market Value MLC</i>	<i>Number of Titles published</i>
USA	24'210	26'750	28'265	37'829	304'912
China	9'173	77'080	15'342	128'928	444'000
Germany	5'567	5'567	9'536	9'536	93'600
UK	4'551	3'898	3'875	3'240	184'000
Japan			5'409	785'100	77'910
Korea	2'949	4'212'623	4'879	6'969'316	43'146
France	2'687	2'687	4'401	4'401	95'483
Spain	2'060	2'060	2'708	2'708	76'434
Brazil	1'645	5'359	2'239	7'294	467'835
Italy	1'645	1'645	1'838	1'838	64'117

Table 2: The biggest publishing markets in 2014 for which figures are available 2015

<i>Country</i>	<i>Revenue M€</i>	<i>Revenue MLC</i>	<i>Market Value M€</i>	<i>Market Value MLC</i>	<i>Number of Titles published</i>
USA	22'918	27'980	29'483		
China	10'578	79'118			448'000
Germany	5'547	5'547	9'322	9'322	87'134
UK	4'587	3'590			220'330
Japan			5'501	754'450	76'465
Korea					
France	2'652	2'652	4'268	4'268	98'306
Spain	2'196	2'196			78'508
Brazil	1'650	5'408			501'371
Italy	1'576	1'576	1'774	1'774	63'922

Source: Annual Report October 2014 - October 2015 Global Publishing and Reading Statistics.

In this vein, lecturers should be encouraged to start uploading their teaching materials electronically and become online publishers while students offering technical education programs need to be encouraged to access eBooks for academic purposes.

Technical & Vocational Education

Ogundele (2010) viewed Technical Education as, the aspect of knowledge, which involves training with special manipulative skills, creative minds, and attitudes required to practice a career for the benefit of that individual and the society. The mindset is to train the individual to be self-reliant, and well productive. To buttress this, the National Policy of Education (NPE, 2013) published by the Federal Government of Nigeria defines Technical Education as that aspect of education, which involves the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical and applied skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of the economic and social lives. The mind-set is to train the individual to be self-reliant, and well productive. This was what led to the formulations of the following goals of Technical Education in Nigeria.

The goals of Technical Education according to N.P.E. (2013) shall be to:

- i. provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advance craft and technical levels;
- ii. provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial, and economic development; and
- iii. give training and impart the necessary skills to individual for self-reliance economically.

Technical Education Programs

The Technical Colleges include Technical College at all level, Technical Institutions Polytechnics, Colleges of Education (Technical) and Universities where some technical/technological education programs are offered among others such as: Building technology, Telecommunications, Electrical/electronic technology, Automobile technology, Metalwork technology, Engineering/technology, and Woodwork technology. The Curriculum consists of General education, Theory and related courses, Workshop Practice, Industrial training/production work, and Entrepreneurial training. The students of these programs are equally trained to be self-employed or pick a job in the industry as this depends on their choice. However, students offering TVET programs

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should be able to access eBooks across the globes that are up to date and relevant in their various disciplines for academic purposes.

Benefits of eBooks

The emergence of eBooks has brought great relief to the society. The impact is felt everywhere including those materials used for producing paper, publishing books, and the rate of circulating or distributing papers. This is because millions of people can access information from eBooks at the same time without waiting for one another, with less transport and time spent.

The publishing industries in conjunction with media industries have experienced and are currently experiencing the rate of growth in eBook technology over the paper printing technology. Various websites are now hosting lots of eBook materials in larger volume than to what the biggest library in the world could host. In today's world of digital technology, the wider and faster ways of publishing e-books by anybody makes more information to be easily accessible in both online and downloaded format. eBooks can be easily copied into the hard drive, flash drive, or on the computer system without adding any weight to one's body. One does not need a printing press machine before becoming a publisher of eBooks, in as much as you can gain access to a computer and get connected to the internet. Such publication can come up in different electronic formats such as the Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF), Microsoft, Google, and other readers like the Sony e-reader.

Reduction of paper in circulation

Various kinds of trees are used for processing and production of papers to print books. This at times is harmful when working on it especially with the use of chlorine. It is widely believed that e-books do not need paper before it can be electronically published. eBooks has drastically reduced the way papers are littering our societies and the rate at which our environment has been polluted. According to Digital Book Readers (2009), e-book is a technology that drastically reduces the use of ink, paper, environmental pollution, and cutting of trees from the bush. Green Press Initiative (2007) observed that the rate at which paper is consumed at a global level is 350 million tons every year. In fact, 290,000 tons of paper was used to produce over 370,000 million of the Harry Potter series of books, at a cost of 5.8 million trees (Digital Book Readers, 2009). In essence, e-book has helped in reducing the rate of paper circulation, which is even harmful to

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human beings when it is burnt and the smoke Carbon (IV) Oxide (CO₂) is inhaled. Because of larger number of production of hard copy books, more than 12.4 million tons of Carbon (IV) Oxide is released into the atmosphere every year (Green Press Initiative 2007). In today's technology with E-books, this has reduced logging of tropical forests and helped in the protection of the climate change where many forest suffered deforestation.

It's Implication to Learning

Despite the positive effects of e-books in our society, there are some negative influences such as plagiarism and fatigue that can users do embark upon except if properly checked.

Plagiarism

According to the Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary (2012), plagiarism means the act of stealing and passing off the ideas or words of another person as one's own (2) using another person's production without crediting the source (3) committing literary theft (4) and presenting as new and original an idea or product derived from an existing source. Plagiarism is not new to students as it is one of the rules institutions of learning are putting on much emphasis to guide students against.

According to plagiarism dot org (n. d.), out of the total number of students surveyed at the national level in US, 54% were guilty of plagiarism. Jones (2011) reported that 92% of the 48 students surveyed in an online business communication course during Fall semester, in 2010 plagiarized at least once. In addition to this, 70% of students among 500 undergraduate students across 60 US campuses were guilty of plagiarism between Fall of 2002 and Spring of 2005 (www.theubpostcom, 2009). Some students will not even want to be creative in their originality, but rather want to use the short cut buttons. Many are now very lazy to think critically and make use of their original ideas instead of copying another's ideas for their own.

Plagiarism is not only peculiar to students alone as many websites are also into the habit of plagiarizing the original work of other people and making it their work. The operators of "www.library.nu" and "www.ifile.it" were discovered to be in an illegal possession of more than 400,000 copyrighted e-books which are made for free. Ironically, they earned an estimated € 8 million Euros annually (\$10,602,400 US annually) before it was shut down in 2012 (Association of American Publishers, 2012).

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Fatigue

Many adults find it difficult to read on screen without any task attached to their readings. Many of these adults will even prefer to print the electronic format for more comprehension sake than to just focus on the online format. This is because of fatigue. Among other things that cause fatigue are lack of adequate sleep, too much reading from the computer screen and other various types of undesirable fonts for eBook productions. According to American Psychological Association (2010), fatigue can be caused by is Web fonts and in conjunction with reading on computer screens. At the end, one imagine the strain and damage this would have caused many eyes. However, many people ended using eyeglasses because of too much strain their eyes were exposed to, while reading from electronic materials.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research method that involves 100 respondents using a survey instruments administered to the selected subjects. The completed questionnaires were retrieved back and analyzed using inferential statistics of chi-square in order to accept or reject the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Research Questions

The following questions were designed to guide this study:

1. Do students have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performances?
2. Do lecture notes/ reading contents uploaded on the college website?
3. Is plagiarism a loophole to publishing eBooks for academic purposes?

Research Hypotheses

A total of three (3) hypotheses were tested using chi-square(X^2) statistical method. The research hypotheses were based on the null hypotheses (H_0). Null hypotheses data analysis was rejected, when the calculated (X^2) value is greater than the critical value at the significant P-value of 0.05 alpha level.

H₀₁ - Students have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performances.

H₀₂ - There is no significant relationship between plagiarism and eBooks for academic purposes.

H₀₃ - Lecturers upload lecture notes / reading contents on the college website.

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Results

Ho₁ - Students have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performances

Table 3 - Chi-Square table showing that students' access to e-Books in the college

S/N	Items	A	U	D	Total	Cal(X ²)	Df	Table of Value X ²	Decision
1.	I have access to electronic-book in the college library.	04	10	86	100	289.76	7	14.1	HO ₁ Rejected
2.	I can use the college electronic-books at will.	11	08	81	100				
3.	Electronic-books is available for download for learning purposes.	00	10	90	100				
4.	The college electronic library is connected with other reputable libraries in the world.	00	09	91	100				
TOTAL		15	37	348	400				

Ho₂ - There is no significant relationship between plagiarism and eBooks for academic purposes.

Table 4 - Chi-Square table showing the significant relationship between plagiarism and eBooks for academic purposes.

S/N	Items	A	U	D	Total	Cal(X ²)	Df	Table of Value X ²	Decision
5.	Students are found of plagiarism other people's work from the internet. book in the college library.	76	06	18	100	274.52	7	14.1	HO ₁ Rejected
6.	Many works cited by students for academic purposes from e-books are not reference.	72	10	18	100				
7.	Students' usage of electronic library can encourage plagiarism. for learning purposes.	43	23	34	100				
8.	E-Books are very easy to copy and paste.	92	00	08	100				
TOTAL		283	39	78	400				

Ho₃ - Lecturers upload lecture notes / reading contents on the college website

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TABLE 5 - Chi-Square table showing that lecturers upload lecture notes / reading contents on the college website.

S/N	Items	A	U	D	Total	Cal(X ²)	Df	Table of Value X ²	Decision
9.	I have access to uploaded reading materials from the college website.	15	10	75	100	289.76	7	14.1	HO ₁ Rejected
	book in the college library								
10.	I can use the college electronic-books at will	19	21	70	100				
11.	Electronic-books are available for download for learning purposes.	14	12	74	100				
12.	Students can borrow electronic-books from other international servers.	00	14	86	100				
TOTAL		48	57	295	400				

Discussion

From Table 3, the hypothesis testing on Students have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performances shows that the calculated value (x^2) of 289.76 is greater than the critical value of 7. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that, students do not have access to electronic-books in the college to improve their academic performances.

From Table 4, the hypothesis testing on the significant relationship between plagiarism and eBooks for academic purpose shows that the calculated value (X^2) of 274.52 is greater than the critical value of 7 at 0.05 alpha level. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that, there is a significant relationship between plagiarism and eBooks for academic purpose. This was supported by the Association of American Publishers (2012) that discovered the operators of www.library.nu and www.ifile.it to be in an illegal possession of more than 400,000 copyrighted e-books which are made for free. Ironically, they earned an estimated € 8 million Euros annually (\$10,602,400 US annually) before it was shut down in 2012.

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From Table 5, the hypothesis testing on Lecturers upload lecture notes / reading contents on the college website shows that the calculated value (χ^2) of 289.76 is greater than the critical value of 7. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that, lecturers do not upload lecture notes / reading contents on the college website.

The study revealed that lecturers are not yet using the college portal to upload teaching and learning materials thereby, having no idea on publishing online. In today's world of digital technology, the wider and faster ways of publishing e-books by anybody makes more information to be easily accessible in both online and downloaded format.

The study revealed that eBooks could easily breed plagiarism among college students unless properly checked. Jones (2011) reported that 92% of the 48 students surveyed in an online business communication course during Fall semester, plagiarized at least once, supported this. In addition to this, 70% of students among 500 undergraduate students across 60 US campuses were guilty of plagiarism between Fall of 2002 and Spring of 2005 (www.theubpostcom, 2009).

Conclusion

Despite the fact that, eBooks are in high demands and it is making big sales over some other technologies like our mobile phones, there is a need for every college library to get connected in order to acquire millions of eBook readers for her students. The usage of eBooks will certainly help in reducing cost, the rate of paper circulation, which is even harmful to human beings when it is burnt and carbon dioxide is inhaled and logging of tropical forests which has contributed to climate change where many forest suffered deforestation. While eBooks are very important as a new technological device for easy publishing and information dissemination, in this digital era, the issue of plagiarism must be properly checked and put in place in order to discourage students from plagiarizing so that they could be creative in their originality.

Recommendations

In respect of the essence of the importance of eBooks in the society, the following recommendations are made:-

1. All institution bodies concerned should device a means of encouraging lecturers to publish eBooks and check student's plagiarism as this is one of the issues of electronic books.
2. Much emphasis should be placed on computer-based examination to that of paper pencil work.
3. Schools and colleges should begin to practice the habit of going paperless in circulating and communicating information, conducting examination, and placement of results.
4. The society should create more awareness on the need to drastically reduce the amount of papers in circulation to cut down paper wastage, environmental pollution, deforestation, and cost.

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